

TODAY'S BIG CHALLENGE OF FOOD SAFETY

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Abstract. This article is devoted to modern problems of food security in the world and its features in the country.

Key words: food, food security, food industry, agricultural products, livestock products.

Аннотация. Данная статья посвящена современным проблемам продовольственной безопасности в мире и ее особенностям в стране.

Ключевые слова: продовольственные товары, продовольственная безопасность, продовольственная промышленность, сельскохозяйственные товары, продукция животноводства.

INTRODUCTION. There is no doubt that with the advancements in the sphere of Technology, other fields like medicine, education, and food production around the world are improving than ever before to provide enough food and increase the chances of humanity to live and eat well on Earth. But there is one concern that needs an immediate answer. How long will this situation last? That's very interesting for many people, researcher and scientists. Because we are all aware of the pace that human population is growing and its impact on the provision of food.

In 1798, the English economist Robert Malthus predicted that this trend would not be stable in the future and that the rapid growth rate would collapse. This meant that the number of undernourished people around the world would be very high and millions of people would die of starvation every year. This prophecy began to come true in the 19th century, and in the 20th century, there were many famines in the world, and in the 21st century, obesity remains the main cause of death from heart disease and cancer.

ANALYSIS OF LITERATURE. Today, there is no single definition of the concept of food safety. In this regard, the theory of food safety has not been fully explained and there are different opinions and approaches to explain its essence. According to YE.V. Serova, food security means the level of providing the main part of the population with food products necessary for leading a normal lifestyle. V.S. According to Balabanov and YE.N. Borisenko, food security is a guarantee of satisfying the country's demand for food on the basis of consumption and creation of reserves in a certain period, while ensuring the safety of manufactured products. K.V.Frolov, A.V.Gordeyev, O.A.Maslennikova and other researchers define food security as follows: providing the citizens of

the country with their needs for vital and useful food products in the required volume and assortment through their own sources.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS. In America, where people thought that there would be no famine, about 9 million people die every year due to diseases caused by famine. Every year, more people die from diseases such as OIDs, malaria, and tuberculosis. The saddest thing is that most of the victims are children.

Famine kills more people than the 72 smallest countries combined. But food insecurity is not the only cause of death. Another factor is lack of quality nutritional products in everyday life.

In most of the Western countries, the products in the supermarkets are suitable for human consumption, but in other countries, such as Syria, the situation is difficult. In Syria, women have to stand in line for up to 7 hours for a piece of bread. Making this situation worse, climate change will also have an impact on our food. These climate changes are leading to water shortages even in hot countries. As a result, the lands that have yielded crops for many years are being brought to a state of drought. Another factor that threatens the food supply is the growing efforts to grow food.

Therefore, people growth is not the one harming the food security. Malfunctioning of the supply system is also main factor causing plenty damage. One of the problems is that 1/3 of the world's food is wasted. This means that 1.3 million tons of food is wasted every year. We can see that there is no problem with supply and demand. Only problem we have is about production and distribution.

Most importantly, the articles topic is very heated just because the best selling product in the small business sector is food. Food safety guarantees our survival. In order to achieve more profit in production, the use of intensive form of agriculture was switched. Although this method allows us to get more crops at a lower price, it causes great damage to the quality of the product and the environment. As a result of carrying out animal husbandry in very small areas, the damages caused over the years have been ignored. Now is the time to make up for the damage caused by careless food production.

Losses of up to 80% are expected in the fishing industry. Regardless of size, age and species, fish are being killed. Losses in this picture are predicted to deprive the whole world of seafood by 2048, and this situation is directly related to food security. Another sad fact is that 80% of the antibiotic drugs produced by the pharmaceutical industry in the United States of America are produced for use in livestock. Currently, animals are bred so densely in farms specializing in

livestock breeding that in some cases of disease, antibiotics are used to save the animals. This situation causes serious damage to human health through consumption of food supply. But antibiotics alone cannot be blamed for this. It has been found that raising animals for food produces more toxic gases than the entire transportation sector. Ranching may also be a major cause of deforestation in the Amazon and other forests.

CONCLUSION. As can be seen from the above, agriculture plays an important role in ensuring food security. A lot of work is being done in this regard in our country. In particular, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, in his speech at the joint session of the chambers of the Oliy Majlis, said, "The issues of agricultural reform and ensuring food security are, without a doubt, one of the most important tasks for us. remains. "First of all, great attention will be paid to the consistent development of the agro-industrial complex and its locomotive, i.e. multi-branch farms, which are the driving force," he said.

Since the first years of our country's independence, food safety issues have been in one of the central places in the socio-economic policy of Uzbekistan. Now the issues of improving the well-being and quality of life of the population, providing the population with food are closely related to the problem of ensuring food safety. Therefore, researching the theoretical foundations and priorities of ensuring food safety based on the implementation of the food program in Uzbekistan is the highest goal of our researchers..

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